

GLOBAL RIVER WATER QUALITY WEB-GIS APPLICATION

(Node.js, Vue.js, PostgreSQL)

Global river water quality application (GRWQ App) is a web-based geographic information system, developed in creative cooperation with [Alexander Knoch](#) and [Holger Virro](#). It is an online tool for visual analysis and spatial data observation of river water quality parameters. GRWQ App is built completely with all advantages of JavaScript (Node.js + Vue.js) and power of SQL (PostgreSQL).

Global River Water Quality Web-GIS App

QUASAR

express

PostgreSQL

The main purposes of GRWQ App development are:

- to create a user-friendly web-application for the observation, visualization and analysis of river water quality parameters

- to conduct an engineering experiment with efficient integration of different frameworks, libraries, technologies (Vue.js + Leaflet.js + DGGS H3) and implement original logic into a front-end single page application

Details about dataset:

- Virro, H., Amatulli, G., Kmoch, A., Shen, L., and Uuemaa, E.: GRQA: Global River Water Quality Archive, Earth Syst. Sci. Data, 13, 5483–5507, 10.5194/essd-13-5483-2021, 2021.

Only open source frameworks and libraries were used:

- Express.js (Node.js web application framework)
- Quasar.js (Vue.js based front-end framework)
- Leaflet.js (library for interactive maps)
- DGGS H3 (hexagonal geospatial indexing system)
- Turf.js (advanced geospatial analysis library)
- Lodash.js (JS utility library)

The main features of GRWQ App:

- selecting area of interest
- search for available sites of river water observation in the area
- saving selected sites to CSV or geoJSON files
- calculating basic statistic parameters of observation values (min, max, mean, median, etc)
- selecting among more than 40 water quality parameters from “Biochemical oxygen demand” to “Total suspended solids”
- selecting available river water quality observations by date range
- dynamically
- generated legend for hexagons of the choropleth map

The most interesting features of GRWQ App:

- integration of Vue.js and Leaflet.js without using “common state” – both libraries work independently
- usage of all advantages of Composition API and Pinia store in Vue 3
- implementation of DGGS (Discrete Global Grid Systems) H3 (Hexagonal hierarchical geospatial indexing system) for building the choropleth map on different resolution levels

Useful links:

- YouTube “how-to” video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pLJTKseKyDo>
- Source code of GRWQ App on GitHub: <https://github.com/rmcf/gwq/>
- GRWQ App link: <https://maps.landscape-geoinformatics.org/gwq-spa/>